
A HOLISTIC FRAMEWORK WITH
ANTICOUNTERFEIT AND INTELLIGENCE-BASED
TECHNOLOGIES THAT WILL ASSIST FOOD CHAIN
STAKEHOLDERS IN RAPIDLY IDENTIFYING AND
PREVENTING THE SPREAD OF FRAUDULENT
PRACTICES.

Transparency
& Authenticity
in the Food Chain

watsonproject.eu

Funded by
the European Union

INTRODUCING WATSON

Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action delivering a holistic framework to detect and prevent food fraud across various food value chains.

WHY IT MATTERS

- Early identification and prevention of fraud
- Stronger end-to-end traceability
- Reinforced consumer trust through transparent, tamper-resistant data

FACTS

Funding scheme:

HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01-11

EU contribution:

€ 9,744,008

Duration:

3 years | March 2023 - February 2026

Consortium:

49 partners across 20 European Union (EU) & non-EU countries

Pilot sites:

6 pilots on agri-food value chains

Project coordinator:

University College Dublin

KEY TERMS & ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
DFPP	Digital Food Product Passport
EU	European Union
EVOO	Extra Virgin Olive Oil
EWS	Early Warning System
HSI	Hyperspectral Imaging
NIR	Near-Infrared
IoT	Internet of Things
TRL	Technological Readiness Level
BRL	Business Readiness Level
PGI	Protected Geographical Indication
LC-MS/MS	Liquid Chromatography- tandem Mass Spectrometry
MALDI	Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization
PUF	Physical Unclonable Functions
EPCIS	Electronic Product Code Information Services

HOW WE TEST IT?

Through 6 cross-border pilots the **Watson** framework integrates Artificial Intelligence (AI) and an Early Warning System (EWS), Internet of Things (IoT) data services with interoperability, Blockchain-backed Digital Food Product Passport (DFPP), portable on-site DNA authentication, smart labels, handheld spectroscopy scanners, stakeholder & consumer mobile apps and innovative analytical methods.

WATSON FRAMEWORK

A HOLISTIC TRACEABILITY FRAMEWORK

Watson develops a holistic traceability framework that will integrate data-driven services, intelligence-based toolsets and risk-estimation approaches

AN INSPECTION AND CONTROL CAPABILITY

Watson will advance the inspection and control capabilities of food safety authorities through robust, reliable and rapid methods based on emerging digital technologies

PUBLIC FOOD POLICY AND EU REGULATIONS

Mainstream project results towards relevant policy making organisations and standardisation bodies

USER INTERFACE

Agencies: Early warnings, access to models and data

Stakeholders: Data provision and management, privacy aspects

Consumers: Integrity verification, fraud detection, access to digital passport

Engineers: Participation in marketplace, provision and testing of algorithm

APPLICATION & INTELLIGENCE

DFPP PUF

FOOD CHAIN PROFILE

Functional Modules Links to Data Sources

DATABASE

Food Fraud Prevention Data-based Attribute Verification Food Fraud Detection Risk-based Food Fraud Decision

EWS BASED ON ML/AI

DATA SOURCES

IoT Sensors	Spectroscopic Sensors
DNA-based Sensor	Multi-sensor Food Scanning Device
Food Chains Historical Data	External Data Sources

Traceability Identification, LOT, EPCIS, QR
Interoperability Data transformations, semantics, aggregation
Blockchain Smart contracts, IPFS, data verification

PARTNERS

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Extra Virgin Olive Oil

Meat

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IMPROVING TRACEABILITY IN THE WINE SUPPLY CHAIN

PORTUGAL

FRAUD & TRACEABILITY RISKS ADDRESSED

- limited chain transparency
- origin misrepresentation
- quality manipulation of wine characteristics across production stages
- accessibility of information to visually impaired consumers

LEAD

WHERE IN THE VALUE CHAIN DOES THE PILOT DEVELOP ACTIVITIES

FARMING ▶ LOGISTICS ▶ PRODUCTION ▶ CONSUMPTION

Data Used

Environmental data, Farm data, weather and historical grape and wine production, geolocation, transportation routes, pilot wine spectrums, pilot data of wine images captured by smartphones

Watson Tools used

- The EWS
- The DFPP
- Hyperspectral scanning technology for farmers and wine producers
- Colour scanning technology and label processing for visually impaired consumer

End-users targeted

- Food authorities
- Grape and wine producers
- Visually impaired consumers

HOW THE PILOT WORKS

SCENARIO 1

EWS to detect grape and wine production yield inconsistencies

Objective

Spotting wine tampering by checking if the amount of wine made matches the expected grape harvest from its true origin

For whom

Food authorities

Food fraud

Chain transparency

Data path

Devices (Field IoT) ▶
Watcher (Ingest IoT data) ▶
Interoperability (Normalize data) ▶ EWS (Predict & detect issue alerts) ▶ Authority (receive notifications/alerts)

HOW THE PILOT WORKS

SCENARIO 2

Wine producer verifying the origin of the grapes

Objective

Enable the winery to confirm that incoming grape batches truly come from the declared vineyard(s) and route by checking geolocation and transport data exposed in the DFPP

For whom

Wine producers / cellar intake managers.

Food fraud

Origin substitution, undeclared mixing of grapes, misrepresentation of geographic origin, tampering with transport route logs

Data path

Devices (Transport IoT GNSS & env sensors) ▶ Watcher (ingest IoT data) ▶ Interoperability (normalize & publish) ▶ Blockchain (immutable storage) ▶ DFPP (display batch route & origin) ▶ Producer (verify at winery intake)

HOW THE PILOT WORKS

SCENARIO 3

Wine producer verifying wine characteristics during different stages

Objective

Let growers and wineries do quick, low-cost, non-invasive checks of grape and wine quality on-site with a portable hyperspectral device. It gives coarse, real-time readings and builds a dataset to link what's in the grapes to what ends up in the wine

For whom

Grape growers, wine producers, cellar intake/QC teams

Food fraud

Coarse screening to flag potential issues such as unusual spectral patterns inconsistent with the declared grape/wine profile

Data path

Portable hyperspectral sensor
▶ smartphone app (captures spectra + time/geotag)
▶ 4G/Wi-Fi ▶ INESC TEC server (processing, dataset & basic analytics)
▶ producer dashboard/report for on-site decisions

HOW THE PILOT WORKS

SCENARIO 4

Boosting the confidence of visually impaired consumers

Objective

Help visually impaired people quickly check what type of wine they have (red / white / rosé) and hear key label information through an easy mobile app that listens to the camera and speaks the result

For whom

Visually impaired consumers (end-users) and accessibility support organisations

Food fraud

Consumer trust: Provides coarse, consumer-level reassurance and flags obvious mismatches between label claims and visible features

Data path

Smartphone camera (RGB image capture) ▶ Mobile app (on-device image processing: wine-colour classifier + label detection/OCR) ▶ Optional Cloud API (advanced label lookup / DFPP query & NLP) ▶ Text-to-Speech audio output to the user

THE OUTCOMES & BENEFITS

How Watson helps the wine sector and consumers

KEY OUTCOMES

- ✓ Trace grape origin, detect tampering, certify wine with a DFPP and restore trust
- ✓ Complement the grapes traceability with in-situ analysis to the wine produced
- ✓ Facilitate the visually impaired consumers integration in the wine market, enabling mechanisms to automatically receive audio insights from the bottles

BENEFITS

Food Authorities

Get early alerts about inconsistencies to guide inspections

Wine producers

Reassure the authenticity of their product and protect protected designation of origin / Protected Geographical Indication (PGI) value

Consumers

Gain confidence that the wine truly comes from its claimed region

Visually impaired consumers

Gain confidence in navigating choices

LESSONS LEARNT

Not All Outliers are Errors

On-site collaboration shows unique producer methods can look like data errors. We must be flexible, separating valuable, real-world insights from actual value chain inconsistencies

Show, Don't Just Tell

Hands-on tech demos connect users with tools in their real context, outperforming passive talks

From Prototype to Product

Prototyping isn't the finish line. Future events must give industrial partners a "stage," actively promoting the industrialization needed to bring these technologies to market

& NEXT STEPS

- Extend the approach to more vineyards in Portugal, with fully autonomous deployment of the technologies in the field
- Connect EWS results to blockchain-based product passports
- Enhance grape- and wine-scanning accuracy to deliver high-fidelity, real-time inputs to the EWS and DFPP

ENGAGE WITH US

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The Food Detectives | Episode 5
Which Grapes Went into Which Bottle?

PRESERVING THE AUTHENTICITY OF SPANISH NORTHWEST HONEY

SPAIN

FRAUD & TRACEABILITY RISKS ADDRESSED

- Adulteration with cheaper sugars/syrups (mainly with syrups of corn and rice)
- Mislabelling of botanical origin (Coast / Mountain / Forest or generic Asturias honey)
- Limited transparency along production–processing–retail
- Accessibility of traceability information to consumers

LEAD ASINCAR

WHERE IN THE VALUE CHAIN DOES THE PILOT DEVELOP ACTIVITIES

PROCESSING ► PACKAGING ► RETAIL ► CONSUMPTION

Data Used

Physico-chemical properties, pollen analysis, sample metadata, Near-Infrared (NIR) spectra, hyperspectral images, logistics/production history, monitoring data

End-users targeted

- Food control authorities
 - ◊ PGI Asturias Honey
 - ◊ Regional Government
- Packers
- Consumers

Watson Tools used

- Low cost, easy to use and handheld AI-assisted NIR sensor device for:
 - ◊ Detection of added sugars or syrups in honey
 - ◊ Detection of mislabelling of botanical origin
- Portable AI-assisted Hyperspectral Imaging (HSI) technology for:
 - ◊ Detection of added sugars or syrups in honey
 - ◊ Detection of mislabelling of botanical origin
- EWS for honey chain alerts (food control bodies)
- Mobile app for consumer-facing traceability info

HOW THE PILOT WORKS SCENARIO 1 & 2

Fast NIR & HSI screening to detect added sugars/syrups in honey

Objective

Give control authorities a quick, low-cost, non-destructive on-site check to flag honey adulterated with added sugars/syrups.

For whom

- Food control authorities
- Packers can use the tools for verifying the origin of the honey they buy for packaging

Food fraud

Adulteration by mixing honey with cheaper sugar syrups

Data path

Handheld NIR/ portable HSI tools ► WATSON NIR/HSI software (model inference) ► Result ("pure honey/ adulterated") ► Store NIR spectra/ HSI images + metadata.)

HOW THE PILOT WORKS

SCENARIO 3 & 4

Fast NIR & HSI screening to **detect mislabelling of botanical origin**

Objective

Use NIR and HSI sensor devices to coarsely verify the claimed botanical origin classes "Coast"/"Mountain"/"Forest" or "Generic Asturian Honey" if the sample does not fit any type during routine controls.

For whom

- Food control authorities
- Producers and packers can use the tools to support the correct label according to the botanical origin of the honey

Food fraud

Mislabelling of botanical origin - "Coast", "Mountain", "Forest" or "Generic Asturian Honey"

Data path

Handheld NIR / portable HSI tools ▶ Device app (origin-class model) ▶ On-screen class + probability ▶ Store spectra/image metadata to pilot database

HOW THE PILOT WORKS

SCENARIO 5

EWS for the honey value chain

Objective

Aggregate value-chain data to warn control bodies early about potential tampering hotspots or anomalous trends.

For whom

Food control authorities

Food fraud

Tampering/adulteration patterns detected from multivariate signals

Data path

Pilot datasets (production, storage, transport) ▶ Processing layer ▶ Predictive layers ▶ EWS dashboard alerts to authorities.

HOW THE PILOT WORKS

SCENARIO 6

Mobile consumer app for traceability information

Objective

Let consumers view key traceability facts of honey products in an accessible, simple application

For whom

Consumers

Food fraud

Consumer trust: Raises transparency and consumer confidence by surfacing verifiable product info

Data path

Smartphone app (scan) ► backend (traceability data) ► on-screen output

THE OUTCOMES & BENEFITS

How Watson helps the honey sector and consumers

KEY OUTCOMES

- ✓ Fast, non-destructive screening workflows (NIR/HSI) institutionalised for food authorities and quality control bodies
- ✓ Actionable early warnings for authorities and control bodies
- ✓ Transparent consumer info via the mobile app

BENEFITS

Food Authorities

- On-site analysis obtaining real-time results. Screening more lots with fewer resources
- Earlier, data-driven alerts

Honey value chain

- More credible PGI
- Reduced exposure to market dilution by fakes

Consumers

- Greater confidence in origin & quality
- easy access to information

LESSONS LEARNT

Honey samples stored in bad conditions (temperature, humidity) can produce errors

Sample preheating to 30°C is crucial for avoiding errors in the final results

NIR and HSI technologies are able to detect adulterated honey samples, as well as to identify botanical origin

& NEXT STEPS

- Extend the AI-assisted NIR/HSI screening methods to monofloral products
- Increase the dataset for improving algorithms accuracy
- Extend the approach to other PGI honey products in Spain

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ASINCAR

The Food Detectives | Episode 4
Is your honey really made by bees?

RAPID TRACEABILITY OF EXTRA VIRGIN OLIVE OIL

FRAUD & TRACEABILITY RISKS ADDRESSED

- Stakeholders' accountability along production-processing-retail
- Limited value chain transparency and data integrity against violations
- Detection of admixtures with cheaper oils
- Origin and varietal mislabelling and false origin claims
- Limited accessibility of traceability information to consumers

ITALY GREECE

LEAD

THE NEW GUARDIANS OF OLIVE OIL BRINGING RADICAL TRANSPARENCY TO EVOO

- Rapid DNA testing confirms the oil's genetic identity, and that data is secured on a blockchain to create a DFPP
- The result? What's on the label is guaranteed to be in the bottle
- An AI-powered EWS also assesses fraud risks, keeping authorities one step ahead

Where in the value chain does the pilot develop activities

FIELD ► MILL ► PRODUCER/RETAILERS ► CONSUMER

Data used

- **Field:** harvesting data, orchard geolocation, qualitative and quantitative data, genetic characterization of cultivars, olive batch IDs, carrier documents
- **Mill & Storage:** processing and storage data, olive oil lots/batches IDs, volumes, genetic profiling
- **Producer/Trading/Retailer:** olive oil IDs, logistics, bottling events, lot packaging, genetic profiling
- **Consumer:** QR code to offer access to DFPP

End-users targeted

- Farmers who buy olives
- Mill owners or olive oil producers/wholesalers or retailers.
- Consumers
- Food authorities

Watson Tools used

- Portable DNA testing
- The EWS
- The DFPP

HOW THE PILOT WORKS

SCENARIO 1

Farmer:

Tracing the olives from field to mill.

Objective

Register cultivation and harvest data of the fields (who/where/when) and establish their genetic profile

For whom

Farmers, owners of mills

Food fraud

Olives of undeclared origin, cultivar substitution and false quantities before milling

Data path

Field metadata + samples ▶ Lab DNA genotyping (reference)
▶ Interoperability ▶ Blockchain (immutable) ▶ DFPP/EWS

HOW THE PILOT WORKS

SCENARIO 2

On-site DNA authentication

at the olive oil facility. Matching olive oil (storage tank) to olives

Objective

The portable DNA based system allows cross-check that the olive oil comes from the declared batches of olives, results are saved in blockchain, which implements the DFPP

For whom

Mill operators, olive oil producers, wholesalers, authorities or regulatory bodies

Food fraud

Adulteration, admixtures, and mislabelling (false claims of origin)

Data path

Portable DNA isolation system and molecular analyser ▶ AI/ML HRM post-processing pipeline ▶ Interoperability ▶ Blockchain ▶ DFPP and EWS

HOW THE PILOT WORKS

SCENARIO 3

Confirms that the olive oil stored in the tank matches bottled, **ensuring product integrity via DNA** testing and sharing it to the blockchain and DFPP

Objective

Keep a continuous, tamper-evident trail of the production chain from storage to bottling, DNA cross-checks are permitted if needed, deliver transparency for consumer

For whom

Producers, traders, retailers, control bodies

Food fraud

Undeclared blending, manipulation of documents and labels, interrupted value chain

Data path

Storage/blending events ▶ Interoperability ▶ Blockchain ▶ DFPP (lot/item pages) ▶ optional DNA cross-check before bottling

HOW THE PILOT WORKS

SCENARIO 4

Scan-to-see: consumer obtains access to the product's DFPP

Objective

The consumer scans the QR code and obtains information on the DNA identity of the EVOO inside the bottle, its origin and relevant production data. The objective is to increase trust and transparency

For whom

Consumers

Food fraud

EVOO claims are visible and verifiable to the consumer

Data path

QR code ▶ DFPP (blockchain-backed page) ▶ transparent history from field to store

THE OUTCOMES & BENEFITS

How **Watson** helps the EVOO sector and consumers

KEY OUTCOMES

- ✓ **WORLD-FIRST** - Successful on-site DNA authentication (Technological Readiness Level (TRL) 7), moving testing from the lab to the field
- ✓ End-to-end blockchain traceability accessible via DFPP
- ✓ EWS for prediction of fraud risks to alert authorities

BENEFITS

Food Authorities

Faster on-site DNA screening for fraud detection

EVOO producers / retailers

DNA proof of correspondence between content and what is declared on the documents

Consumers

Scan-and-see transparency, increased evidence of EVOO origin and quality

LESSONS LEARNT

Opened path for on-site DNA testing in the olive oil industry leveraging the capacities to detect fraud

In the context of fraud detection, DNA technologies can complement regulatory approved chemical ones and fill their limitations

DNA-based driven traceability using on-site systems enhances digitization, and allows interoperability with other systems based on Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs) such as blockchain and DFPPs

& NEXT STEPS

- Disseminate the results of the WATSON technologies to the research community, Member States, EU policy makers, industry, innovators and civil society/citizens.
- Identify new funding opportunities and scale TRL and BRL levels
- Access EU and private funds to accelerate market uptake

ENGAGE WITH US

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The Food Detectives | Episode 6
Upcoming

IDENTIFYING ADULTERATION IN THE MEAT CHAIN

GERMANY

FRAUD & TRACEABILITY RISKS ADDRESSED

- **Feeding claims:** selling grain-fed beef as grass-fed
- **Water-weight tricks:** injecting protein hydrolysates into chicken breast to increase weight
- **Hidden organs:** mixing organ meat into minced beef without telling the buyer
- **Wrong species:** adding meat from other animal species into minced beef

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LEAD

MRI
Max Rubner-Institut

WHERE IN THE VALUE CHAIN DOES THE PILOT DEVELOP ACTIVITIES

Data Used

Spectroscopy (NIR/Vis) from fat and muscle for feeding-regime checks, Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization (MALDI) imaging of amino-acid distributions (hydrolysate injection in chicken), Liquid Chromatography-tandem Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) marker peptides for detecting organ meat in beef, MALDI peptide fingerprints for foreign species detection in minced beef, DNA metabarcoding for species identification and quantification of pork in minced beef, plus sample metadata (origin, cut, storage, timepoints)

FARM ▶ SLAUGHTERHOUSE

▶ PROCESSING PLANT ▶ RETAILER/BUTCHER

End-users targeted

- Public food control authorities
- Quality-control laboratories/industry
- Big retail companies

Watson Tools used

- Handheld NIR device for rapid, non-invasive grass- vs. grain-fed beef checks
- Analytical methods for chicken hydrolysates, organ adulteration, and species substitution

HOW THE PILOT WORKS SCENARIO 1

Distinguishing grain-fed from grass-fed beef with a handheld NIR/Vis scanner

sugars/syrups in honey

Objective

Give control bodies and QC teams a quick, non-invasive way to check feeding claims (grass vs grain) on the spot

For whom

Public food control authorities and the quality-control industry

Food fraud

Chain transparency

Data path

Handheld NIR/Vis device ▶ App on tablet/PC (stores spectra + metadata) ▶ Classification model (grass/grain) ▶ Result saved to pilot database (for evaluation)

HOW THE PILOT WORKS SCENARIO 2

Identifying chicken breast **injected with protein hydrolysates**

Objective

Flag chicken meat artificially “water-weighted” with added hydrolysates using a high-sensitivity lab method

For whom

Public food control bodies

Food fraud

Undeclared addition of foreign protein-hydrolysate

Data path

Sampling (point of sale/ processing) ▶ Microscopy ▶ MALDI-MS imaging (amino-acid distribution) ▶ Screening result + spectra stored for evaluation

HOW THE PILOT WORKS SCENARIO 3

Detecting organ meat in minced beef via LC-MS/MS using marker peptides

Objective

Spot undeclared organ additions in cooked/heated minced beef using heat-stable peptide markers

For whom

Public food control authorities and QC labs (including retailers’ labs)

Food fraud

Hidden organ substitution in minced beef

Data path

Pilot sample prep (known mixtures for validation) ▶ LC-MS/MS run ▶ Marker detection ▶ Method performance evaluation (1. qualitative: false positive/false negative rates, 2. assessment of the quantitative potential: linearity, trueness, precision) ▶ Store outcomes to pilot database.

HOW THE PILOT WORKS

SCENARIO 4

Detecting pork fractions in minced beef

Objective

Find undeclared species mixed into beef using fast MALDI screening and DNA metabarcoding and quantify pork in minced beef

For whom

Public food control authorities and QC labs

Food fraud

Species substitution in minced beef

Data path

Pilot sample prep ▶ MALDI fingerprinting and DNA metabarcoding ▶ MALDI: spectra evaluation and regression model, DNA:Marker quantification ▶ Store outcomes to pilot database

THE OUTCOMES & BENEFITS

How Watson helps the meat sector and consumers

KEY OUTCOMES

- ✓ The handheld NIR device provides a fast and reliable tool for differentiating between grass-fed and grain-fed beef
- ✓ MS methods offer selective and accurate detection of hydrolysate injection in poultry meat and of offal in minced beef products
- ✓ DNA metabarcoding reliably detects foreign species in minced beef and offers an approach for the quantification of pork in minced beef products

BENEFITS

Food Authorities

The portable NIR device allows extensive testing of animals to confirm grass-fed status, faster screening due to the simultaneous and selective detection of frauds (various offals, hydrolysates, foreign species)

QC labs & retailers

Reassure the authenticity of their product and increase supplier trustworthiness and business transactions

Consumers

More honest labels (less hidden organs/species, realistic “grass-fed” claims)

LESSONS LEARNT

Sample variability and context matter: measurement time points, cuts, breeds and sample treatments influence analytical results

Each analytical method has specific requirements and limitations that must be considered (time and resource constraints, procedural complexity, compatibility with various sample matrices)

Reference data and databases are essential: Reliable interpretation of data depends on comprehensive reference data and databases

& NEXT STEPS

- **Method optimization and validation:** Assess key performance parameters of all methods for both qualitative and quantitative applications
- **Standardization and reference frameworks:** Account for sample variability (impact of different cuts on MALDI spectra, different types of hydrolysates used for injection of poultry meat)
- **Collaboration and cross validation:** cooperate with official food authorities to compare mass spectrometry approaches with histological methods (injection of hydrolysates) or official reference methods (foreign species)

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The Food Detectives | Episode 2
Beating Fraud from the Farm to the Butcher

IMPROVING TRACEABILITY IN THE BREWERY AND CHEESE CHAINS

FINLAND

FRAUD & TRACEABILITY RISKS ADDRESSED

- Item-level traceability
- Supply-chain transparency for consumers
- Ingredient level information
- Consumer-to-producer communication channel

WHERE IN THE VALUE CHAIN DOES THE PILOT DEVELOP ACTIVITIES

- **Farm & suppliers:** Provides information about ingredients and their origin, production dates
- **Processing:** Provides information about process, ingredients, metrics, dates
- **Retail:** Accepts items into retail. Colour scanning technology and label processing for visually impaired consumer
- **Consumption:** Accesses item-level information and can contact producer directly

Data Used

Ingredient and origin data, Manufacturing conditions & methods at batch and item level, Logistic events, Smartcodes/ DataMatrix managed centrally, each item/batch has a secure identity

End-users targeted

- Consumers
- Industry
- Retail
- Food authorities

Watson Tools used

Smart tags/Smartcodes for item/batch identity (with anti-counterfeit features under development)

HOW THE PILOT WORKS

SCENARIO 1

Increasing transparency in the brewery supply chain inconsistencies

Objective

Let consumers, buyers and authorities scan a code to see who made the beer, which raw materials were used, and key processing steps - all in one place

For whom

Consumers, food control bodies, and supply-chain partners

Food fraud

Chain transparency

Data path

Malt & ingredient data ▶ Brewery batch record ▶ Packaging with Smartcode ▶ Ucode App ▶ Consumer/authority scan & view

HOW THE PILOT WORKS

SCENARIO 2

Increasing transparency in the dairy supply chain

Objective

Give each cheese batch/item a smart identity so staff and consumers can track it from milk intake to retail, and so producers can message customers if needed (a targeted recall)

For whom

Consumers, food control bodies, and supply-chain partners

Food fraud

Chain transparency

Data path

Dairy operator logs milk batch ▶ Cheese products linked to smart tags ▶ State changes (in transport /in retail) via scans ▶ Consumer/authority scan & view

THE OUTCOMES & BENEFITS

How Watson helps the cereal & dairy sector and consumers

KEY OUTCOMES

- ✓ Item-level traceability for both chains (scans at production, retail, and consumer levels)
- ✓ Higher trust among stakeholders via a single, shareable history per batch/item
- ✓ Connection between consumer and producer, without middlemen

BENEFITS

Food Authorities

Rapid verification at point of control. All the data available before the inspection. Predictive actions if needed

Industry

Clear chain-of-custody, direct feedback loop with customers

Consumers

Scan and verify claims, get recall messages if necessary

LESSONS LEARNT

Smart tags increased consumer trust and supply-chain transparency, standard barcodes often fail to engage

Built to integrate with authorities' systems. Piloting was restricted where equivalent tools existed, yet the approach is easily adopted elsewhere

Much data remains non-digital, creating interoperability bottlenecks that hinder automated data collection

& NEXT STEPS

- Implementation of smart tag solutions in other products categories
- Development of the authority level smart tag system. Also applicable for other logistic stakeholders
- Further utilization of the blockchain to improve data input
- Further implementation of smart labelling and functional inks (temperature sensitive) in the smart tags

ENGAGE WITH US

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The Food Detectives | Episode 3
Honest Cheese and Transparent Beer?

INCREASING TRANSPARENCY IN THE WHITE FISH CHAIN — FROM CATCH TO CONSUMER

NORWAY

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FRAUD & TRACEABILITY RISKS ADDRESSED

- Origin substitution or undocumented swaps between landing and storage.
- Broken chain-of-custody when documentation and goods diverge
- Mislabeled packs reaching consumers without verifiable history

LEAD SINTEF

WHERE IN THE VALUE CHAIN DOES THE PILOT DEVELOP ACTIVITIES

- ON-VESSEL CATCH ▶
- EXTERNAL COLD STORAGE ▶
- TRANSPORTATION ▶ PROCESSING/PACKING
- ▶ CONSUMPTION

Data Used

Vessel logs, AIS/GPS, pallet IDs, temperature/handling events, storage hand-offs, processing lots, nutritional/label fields, consumer pack codes. DFPP identifiers to link events end-to-end

End-users targeted

- Authorities
- Industry
- Consumers

Watson Tools used

- The EWS
- The DFPP

HOW THE PILOT WORKS SCENARIO 1

Trace the catch to external storage with the Watson DFPP

Objective

Capture information from vessel to external storage so each pallet/lot has a verifiable trail users can later view via DFPP

For whom

- Processors
- Buyer

Food fraud

Reduces opportunities for origin substitution and undocumented swaps between landing and storage

Data path

Vessel logs & AIS/GPS ▶ pallet temp/sensors ▶ Interoperability layer (GS1/EPCIS-ready) ▶ Blockchain (tamper-evident records) ▶ DFPP (traceability view)

HOW THE PILOT WORKS SCENARIO 2

Premium product line with DFPP for consumers

Objective

Create a one-supplier product line (Hermes catch, processed by Espersen) so consumers can scan a code and see the product's journey from catch to pack

For whom

Consumers (scan to check origin & processing)

Food fraud

Makes chain-of-custody visible, discourages mislabelling or substitution by showing the data, not just claims

Data path

Vessel + storage data ► processing lots & label info ► Interoperability ► Blockchain ► DFPP (consumer view via QR tags)

HOW THE PILOT WORKS SCENARIO 3

EWS for fishery activities concerns

Objective

Give control authorities a dashboard that flags unusual patterns (activity in no-fishing zones, route anomalies) based on environmental, location and management data

For whom

Public control bodies

Food fraud

Supports earlier detection and targeted inspections where the risk is higher

Data path

Vessel AIS/GPS + environment ► Interoperability ► EWS processing & predictive layers ► Explainability + visualisation ► Alerts to authorities

THE OUTCOMES & BENEFITS

How Watson helps the fish sector and consumers

KEY OUTCOMES

- ✓ **Transparency:** Richer, verified data along the chain, made accessible through and curated for users via DFPP
- ✓ **Trust:** Consumers and buyers can verify origin and handling themselves, strengthening confidence in the product
- ✓ **Prevention:** Authorities receive early warnings, enabling focused, risk-based inspections and faster fraud detection

BENEFITS

Authorities

Better targeting of inspections where risk is highest via EWS alerts

Industry

(catchers, processors, retailers)

Clear chain-of-custody to better target recalls and protect brand value and access premium markets

Consumers

Scan and verify the origin, handling, and quality of the fish

LESSONS LEARNT

Extreme environmental conditions challenge sensor durability Cold (below -25°C) and humid environments pose significant challenges for sensor performance and battery longevity, especially for long-term deployments

Data sharing readiness varies across the value chain Not all organizations in the supply chain are technically or organizationally prepared to share data in ways that support traceability and transparency

Positive reception of Watson innovations Many stakeholders express interest and recognize the value of the solutions developed in Watson, particularly regarding improved traceability and trust

& NEXT STEPS

- **Enhance sensor and packaging resilience**
Develop robust sensor-and-packaging solutions to prevent data loss in challenging conditions
- **Propose standards for data exchange**
Adopt common data-exchange standards to enable interoperable traceability across the supply chain
- **Promote transparency as an industry norm**
Foster industry-level transparency adoption so digital traceability can deliver its full value for seafood

ENGAGE WITH US

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